

Anticancer Activity of *Gnidia glauca* Extracts in Human Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract : *Gnidia glauca* is a semi-woody herb of thymelaeaceae family traditionally used as fish poison in India. It is also found in Sri Lanka and Africa. In the present study, potential anticancer effect of n-hexane and ethanolic extracts of *Gnidia glauca* in human breast cancer cells was investigated. Human breast cancer cells (MCF-7) were cultured as monolayers in RPMI 1640 medium. The cells were cultured for 48 hours to allow growth and achieve about 80% confluence in 96-well culture plates. The cells were treated with various concentrations of *Gnidia glauca* (0.1-100 mg/mL) for 72 hours. Percentage of viable cells after treatment was assessed using a sulforhodamine B colorimetric assay. Both n-hexane and ethanolic extract showed significant cytotoxic activity on MCF-7 cancer cells. This study supports the notion of using *Gnidia glauca* as a novel anticancer agent for breast cancer.

Keywords : 96 well plate, anticancer activity, *Gnidia glauca*, MCF-7

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